

Assessing the agroecological impact of digital tools in livestock production: A systematic review

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ABSTRACT

With the emergence of digital technologies, livestock production is experiencing a transformation. To ensure a transition towards more sustainable livestock systems, such as agroecologically based livestock production, consideration needs to be given to the environmental and social impacts of digitalization. Thus, the main aim of this study was to map digital tools used in the livestock sector and assess them in terms of economic, environmental and social impact, and define their potential as enablers of agroecology. A query search on the Web of Science database was followed by the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) methodology to identify relevant articles. In total, 73 articles were included in this analysis. The results indicated that most of the digital tools identified are used for managing ruminants (78.1%), with 89% of those tools used for monitoring tasks. The most frequently used digital tool and platform were the RGB/RGB-D camera (42.5%) and the stationary platform (61.6%), respectively. The digital tools contributed mainly to input reduction (e.g., feed, water) (58.9%), which corresponds to the first tier of agroecology. While digital technologies show potential to support agroecological transitions, current applications focus on efficiency rather than systemic change. Future research should explore their role in higher agroecological tiers, with particular attention to participatory design, environmental regeneration, and social equity.

1. Introduction

The livestock sector is facing significant challenges due to environmental pressure, climate change and labour-related factors [1,2]. The sector has been associated with excessive water consumption [3] and pollution, such as bacterial resistance, odour and nitrate leaching from slurry and manure [4], large consumption of fodder crops and consequently a significant occupation of arable farm land that could be used for other crops for human consumption [5], as well as soil degradation [6] and considerable greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions [7]. Moreover, people from rural areas are moving to cities, leading to an increase in the average age of farmers [8]. Additionally, livestock businesses currently face labour shortages due to difficult working conditions [9]. To

overcome these challenges, there is a need to transition current livestock production systems to more sustainable and resilient ones that adopt a more holistic approach in relation to economic, environmental and societal sustainability [10–12].

Agroecology is a holistic approach that can substantially change the way livestock production is carried out by coupling biophysical and socioeconomic processes and components, with the aim of designing and managing more sustainable production systems [12,13]. The Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) has identified ten elements that are used to guide a system's transition to agroecology. These are diversity, responsible governance, recycling, efficiency, synergies, resilience, circular and solidarity economy, human and social values, co-creation and sharing of knowledge, and culture and food traditions [13]. Potentially,

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agroecology can contribute to environmental, societal and economic resilience [14] by incorporating each element in the livestock production processes. Cattle farmers who have adopted various agroecological practices (e.g., alternative feeds, low-input rotational grazing) perceived improved working conditions, health, skills and rewards [15]. Additionally, the use of integrated crop-livestock systems in ruminants under the principles of agroecology can mitigate climate constraints, improve reproductive management and crop pest control, increase income due to the production of energy or nonconventional feedstuff, and contribute to society (e.g., job opportunities) [16]. Moreover, adoption of a circular economy approach for the management of livestock byproducts, like manure, can contribute to restoring the balance between inputs and outputs in livestock farms, as well as create the potential for synergistic development at a landscape scale when integrating other crops (e.g., arable crops, orchards, vineyards) [17]. Thus, agroecology can contribute to incremental or transformational changes of food systems, as identified in the five tiers of agroecology, namely Tier one: reduce inputs; Tier two: substitute with sustainable inputs; Tier three: redesign agricultural systems to incorporate biodiversity; Tier four: reconnect producers and consumers; Tier five: create a just and equitable global food system, as suggested by previous research [18].

Similarly, smart farming and in particular, precision livestock farming, can enable the transition of current livestock production systems to agroecology. Smart farming consists of various digital tools like uncrewed aerial and ground systems, camera sensors, smart collars, weather stations and other Internet of Things (IoT) devices that monitor the animals, the pasture and the environment and optimize operations like breeding, feeding and milking [19–23]. The data collected via these tools are usually processed on web platforms and decision support systems to optimize livestock management [24,25]. Uncrewed aerial systems have been used for cow herding to regulate grazing [26], assessing forage biomass [27] and tracking animal movement [28]. Smart collars and rumen boluses are used for disease and oestrus detection and health monitoring [29–31], while IoT sensors for climate, and livestock inputs (e.g., water and feed consumption) and outputs (e.g., produced milk) monitoring are used to optimize resource use and adjust farm practices to increase productivity while reducing environmental externalities [31, 32]. Moreover, milking robots or automatic milking systems (AMS) revolutionized livestock management by increasing the operation efficiency and decreasing the labour needs [33]. Ground robots are used for collecting eggs from cage-free poultry farms [34] as well as to help in grazing [35] and as cleaning robots in stables. Finally, stationary cameras have been used for animal behavior analysis [36] and vision-based measurements such as body dimension and weight [37].

From the abovementioned, it is clear that the use of digital tools can optimize livestock management and provide significant environmental and social benefits. Although the goals of smart farming and digitalization in agriculture are aligned with the scope of agroecology, their connection is a relatively new concept and underexplored [38,39]. Also, there is a big debate among the supporters and critics of use of digitalization for agroecological transition. Although, the first support this by highlighting the higher yields and optimized decision making while the latter refer to limited autonomy in decision-making and disenfranchisement [40]. Thus, the main aim of this review article is to map digital tools that are used in the livestock sector, as well as to assess them in terms of economic, environmental and social impact to identify their potential as enablers of agroecology.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Search strategy and query design

Relevant information on digital tools for livestock that could act as enablers of agroecology was identified through a systematic literature search using the Web of Science database. For this purpose, a structured query was inserted into the search engine to identify relevant research

articles on 28 February 2025 (Table 1). The query was developed for identifying relevant information for crop, animal and agroforestry production as part of the Horizon Europe and Innovate UK cofunded project Digitalisation for Agroecology (D4AgEcol). The outcomes of this query were further screened to extract livestock-related studies.

2.2. Study selection and PRISMA screening

To focus on contemporary research publications, the selected research articles were published from January 2012 until December 2024. To ensure a systematic and transparent selection process, the literature review followed the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) methodology to map the relevant research articles and ensure a systematic and transparent approach. PRISMA is an evidence-based minimum set of items for reporting in systematic reviews and meta-analyses. PRISMA primarily focuses on the reporting of reviews evaluating the effects of interventions, but can also be used as a basis for reporting systematic reviews with objectives other than evaluating interventions (e.g., evaluating aetiology, prevalence, diagnosis or prognosis) [41].

The queries yielded 2,412 research articles. The first outcomes were filtered to exclude articles that, based on the title and abstract, were unrelated to the study's goal. 1,531 articles were omitted on this basis. Out of the remaining 881 articles, 808 were excluded because they were either inaccessible or irrelevant to the scope of this study based on the entire text. The final number of suitable articles that were evaluated in depth for this study was 73 (Fig. 1).

2.3. Classification

The selected articles were categorized based on characteristics related to livestock (type, farming system type and operation), technology (application, platform, sensor, and software), tier of agroecology, and impact type (economic, environmental and social) following other studies [18,42–45]. The final selection of studies was subjected to qualitative and statistical analysis to extract key insights into existing digital tools for the livestock sector excluding animals for fur production (Table 2).

2.4. Impact categorization and scoring

The collected records were assessed in terms of environmental, economic, and social impacts based on the work performed by Wolters et al. [46] (Table 3).

While assessing digital tools for agroecology within the realms of research articles, research projects, and commercial products, an "Impact Scale" was used to methodically evaluate their implications. This scale, which ranges from "Large Decrease" to "Large Increase," served as the metric for gauging the extent to which these digital tools affect economic, environmental, and social factors. By applying this scale, the impact of each digital tool was categorized by experts, enabling an approach to measure the potential benefits or detriments brought about by these innovations. The scale's categorical nature allowed for impact assessments, highlighting those tools that could substantially improve conditions or those that could potentially create risks or challenges across the sectors assessed. Lastly, numerical values were added for each effect depending on the category (Table 4).

After evaluating the economic, environmental, and social impact, the overall score was computed for each category by summing the scores for each type of impact. A similar technique was utilized to assess the combined economic and environmental impact, as well as the overall impact, which considers economic, environmental, and social impacts. The main reason for combining the economic and environmental impacts was to present their integrated potential in comparison to the social impact, which is usually neglected in research [47]. In these evaluations, the normalized numbers were weighted to account for the

Table 1

Query used in the Web of Science database to identify relevant publications.

Web of Science Database Query

(TS=("Internet of Things") OR TS=("cloud computing") OR TS=("big data") OR TS=("artificial intelligence") OR TS=("machine learning") OR TS=("simulation") OR TS=("augmented reality") OR TS=("additive manufacturing") OR TS=("horizontal and vertical system integration") OR TS=("autonomous robo*") OR TS=("cybersecurity") OR TS=("DSS") OR TS=("decision support") OR TS=("sens*") OR TS=("databas*") OR TS=("ICT") OR TS=("robo*") OR TS=("GPS") OR TS=("GNSS") OR TS=("information syste*") OR TS=("image analys?s") OR TS=("image processing") OR TS=("camera*") OR TS=("video") OR TS=("RFID") OR TS=("eID") OR TS=("ruminal bolus") OR TS=("drafting") OR TS=("walk over weight") OR TS=("thermistore*") OR TS=("smart trap*") OR TS=("e?trap*") OR TS=("insect trap*") OR TS=("UAV*") OR TS=("UAS*") OR TS=("accelerometer*") OR TS=("pedometer*") OR TS=("virtual fencing") OR TS=("RGB") OR TS=("multispectral") OR TS=("hyperspectral") OR TS=("thermal") OR TS=("LIDAR") OR TS=("RADAR") OR TS=("EMI") OR TS=("satellite") OR TS=("UGV*") OR TS=("recording") OR TS=("guidance") OR TS=("steering") OR TS=("reacting") OR TS=("variable rate") OR TS=("monitoring") OR TS=("social network*") OR TS=("social platform*") OR TS=("social media") OR TS=("platform*") OR TS=("aerial") OR TS=("proximal") OR TS=("ground") OR TS=("FMIS") OR TS=("farm management information syste*") OR TS=("blockchain") OR TS=("marketplace*") OR TS=("load cell*") OR TS=("flow meter*") OR TS=("microphone*") OR TS=("feeder*") OR TS=("drinker*") OR TS=("body temperature device") OR TS=("photoelectric sensor") OR TS=("scale") OR TS=("force plat*") AND (TS=("diversit*") OR TS=("knowledge AND (co-creat* OR shar*") OR TS=("synerg*") OR TS=("efficien*") OR TS=("recycl*") OR TS=("value* AND (human OR social)") OR TS=("cultur*") OR TS=("food AND tradition*") OR TS=("responsib* AND govern*") OR TS=("economy AND (circular OR solidarity)") AND (TS=("digital agriculture") OR TS=("digital farming") OR TS=("agroecolog*") OR TS=("agro-ecolog*") OR TS=("sustainable agriculture") OR TS=("precision agriculture") OR TS=("smart farming") OR TS=("smart agriculture") OR TS=("precision livestock farming")) AND (TS=("crop*") OR TS=("vineyard*") OR TS=("vegetable*") OR TS=("orchard*") OR TS=("arable") OR TS=("livestock") OR TS=("poultry") OR TS=("chicken") OR TS=("hen") OR TS=("ruminant*") OR TS=("pig*") OR TS=("goat*") OR TS=("sheep") OR TS=("lamb*") OR TS=("cow*") OR TS=("cattle"))

Fig. 1. The PRISMA workflow diagram of the research articles search.

fact that the environmental impact category has one less type of impact than the economic and social categories [48]. Based on the overall ratings in each individual and combined category, each record was rated as having a low, medium, or high impact (Table 5).

2.5. Statistical analysis

The statistical analysis included the number of research studies published annually. In addition, frequency analysis was performed for the livestock characteristics (type, operation and farming system), the digital tools (scope of use, sensors and platforms), the agroecology and the impact assessment. The results of the statistical analysis are documented in the Appendix.

3. Results and discussion

Fig. 2 shows that the majority of selected articles (67 out of 73) were published after 2021. This may justify the increasing research demand on sustainability in the livestock sector, as smart farming is increasingly recognized as a holistic approach with significant potential [49]. Additionally, there was increasing momentum for a transition to healthier and more sustainable animal products after the COVID-19 crisis, which also contributed to a greater need for research [50,51]. Moreover, the technological advancements led to the development of low-cost sensors and therefore increased use of them in research studies [52,53].

Table 2

Classification of the digital tools under the different topics.

Classes	Options
Farming Type	Ruminants; Poultry; Pigs
Farming System Type	Conventional; Organic; Integrated Management
Operation Type	Pest Control; Monitoring; Marketing; Breeding; Feeding; Animal Health care; Dairy production; Egg production; Meat Production
Application Type	Guidance/Steering; Recording/Monitoring/Mapping; Reacting/VRA (Variable Rate Application)/control; Information/Knowledge Sharing
Platform	Satellite; UAV (Uncrewed Aerial Vehicle); UGV (Uncrewed Ground Vehicle); Crewed Ground Vehicles; Stationary; Wearable; Mobile Ground; Crewed Aerial Vehicles
Sensors	Hyperspectral; Multispectral; Thermal; RGB(Red Green Blue)/RGB-D (Red Green Blue-Depth); LIDAR (Light Detection And Ranging); Weather Station; RFID (Radio Frequency Identification)/eID (electronic Identification); Rumen Bolus; Accelerometer; Load Cell; Sound Sensor; Flow Meter; Temperature Sensor; Weight Sensor; NIRS (Near-Infrared Spectroscopy); Smart Collar; Synthetic Aperture Radar; GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite System); Electronic Plate Meter; Smart Feeder; Force Plate; Moocal Device; pH Sensor; Leg Sensor; Milk Meter; Milk Sensor
Software	Software; FMIS (Farm Management Information System); DSS (Decision Support System); Social Platform; Digital Marketplace
Tier of Agroecology	Tier one: reduce inputs; Tier two: substitute with sustainable inputs; Tier three: redesign agricultural systems to incorporate biodiversity; Tier four: reconnect producers and consumers; Tier five: create a just and equitable global food system

3.1. Livestock farm characteristics and applications of digital tools

Most of the identified research articles were focused on ruminants (78.1%), followed by pigs (15.1%) and poultry (12.3%). This may be explained by the fact that ruminants, despite their lower digestion efficiency compared to monogastric animals (e.g., pigs and poultry), can produce more bioavailable protein and utilize human-inedible forages and byproducts [54,55] (Fig. 3).

As shown in Fig. 4, “Monitoring” was the prevalent operation studied, represented in 89% of the research articles. This highlights a strong focus on digital monitoring animal behaviours (e.g., [53–57]), environmental conditions (e.g., [58,59]), or production processes (e.g., [60–63]). Additionally, “Animal Health Care” ranked second, appearing in 53.4% of studies, underscoring the importance of digital technologies in animal health management (e.g., [64–67]). “Feeding” (28.8%) and “Meat Production” (13.7%) ranked third and fourth, respectively, indicating the moderate attention paid for research and consequently reflecting selective adoption of digital tools to optimise feed and

Table 3
Impacts used for the assessment of the selected research articles.

Impact Type	Impact
Economic Impact	• Productivity
	• Revenue, profit, farm income
	• Input costs
	• Shelf life of product
	• Product quality
Environmental Impact	• Product wastage
	• Air protection
	• Soil protection
	• Water protection
	• Biodiversity protection
Social Impact	• GHG emission
	• Labour time
	• Stress for farmer
	• Amount of heavy physical labour
	• Number and/or severity of personal injury accidents
	• Number and/or severity of accidents resulting in spills, property damage, incorrect application of inputs, etc.
	• Human exposure to chemicals

Table 4
Numerical values assigned per impact type.

Impact	Numerical Value				
	Large Decrease	Small Decrease	No Effect	Small Increase	Large Increase
<i>Economic Impacts</i>					
Productivity	-2	-1	0	+1	+2
Revenue, profit, farm income	-2	-1	0	+1	+2
Input costs	+2	+1	0	-1	-2
Shelf life of product	-2	-1	0	+1	+2
Product Quality	-2	-1	0	+1	+2
Product wastage	+2	+1	0	-1	-2
<i>Environmental Impacts</i>					
Air protection	-2	-1	0	1	+2
Soil protection	-2	-1	0	1	+2
Water protection	-2	-1	0	1	+2
Biodiversity protection	-2	-1	0	+1	+2
GHG emission	+2	+1	0	-1	-2
<i>Social Impacts</i>					
Labour time	+2	+1	0	-1	-2
Stress for farmer	+2	+1	0	-1	-2
Amount of heavy physical labor	+2	+1	0	-1	-2
Number and/or severity of personal injury accidents	+2	+1	0	-1	-2
Number and/or severity of accidents resulting in spills, property damage, incorrect application of inputs, etc.	+2	+1	0	-1	-2
Human exposure to chemicals	+2	+1	0	-1	-2

drinking management as well as enhancing meat yield or quality (e.g., [68–71]). The activities of “Breeding”, “Egg Production”, and “Dairy Production” appeared less frequent (6.8%, 2.7%, and 2.7%, respectively) (e.g., [58,65,72,73]). This can be explained by the fact that these specific operations face greater barriers to implementing digital innovation, like low interest and expensive equipment [74,75].

Table 5
Weights and categorization rules per impact category.

Impact Type	Weight	Numeric Values		
		Low Impact	Medium Impact	High Impact
Economic	1	<4	=>4 and <8	=>8
Environmental	1	<3	=>3 and <7	=>7
Social	1	<4	=>4 and <8	=>8
Economic and Environmental*	0.5	<4	=>4 and <8	=>8
Overall*	0.33	<4	=>4 and <8	=>8

* These refer to normalized values

Fig. 2. Number of articles per year.

Fig. 3. Percentage of relevant articles per livestock type.

Fig. 4. Percentage of relevant articles per operation type.

3.2. Characteristics and use of digital tools in livestock farming

The distribution of research articles highlighting different applications of digital tools in livestock management, categorized per application type, is presented in Fig. 5. The majority of studies focused on “Recording, Monitoring, and Mapping” applications (95.9%). Thus, there is a strong research interest in technologies that allow detailed

Fig. 5. Percentage of relevant articles per application type.

tracking of animal behaviours and health (e.g., [76–81]), environmental factors (e.g., [59,82]), and operational efficiency (e.g., [58,68,83]). Conversely, significantly fewer studies concentrate on “Information and Knowledge Sharing” (4.1%) (e.g., [70,84]), which ranked second, while “Reacting or Variable Rate Application (VRA)/Control mechanisms” (2.7%) (e.g., [85]), and “Guidance or Steering technologies” (1.4%) [61] ranked third and fourth, respectively. Based on this analysis, it can be concluded that the last three application types have not been adequately studied. This can be justified by the demand for higher investments for research due to the needed equipment for the case of “Reacting or Variable Rate Application (VRA)/Control mechanisms” [86]. Also, the specific characteristics of livestock farming, like indoor environment have led to limited interest in research for the case of “Guidance or Steering technologies” [87], while studies on assessing the benefits derived from “Information and Knowledge Sharing” are still at an early stage [88].

Various digital tools are used for livestock management, as shown in Fig. 6. This variation reflects the diverse needs across species, environments, and operations in livestock systems [89]. Specifically, “RGB/RGB-D sensors” were the most frequently used digital tool type, utilized in 42.5% of the analysed research articles. This underscores the importance of visual and depth-sensing cameras for monitoring livestock. Indeed, “RGB/RGB-D sensors” can be used for various purposes like assessing animal behaviour (e.g., [90,77,91,92]), weight estimation (e.g., [73,93,94]), animal identification (e.g., [64,95,]), animal characteristics for breeding (e.g., [96]) and herding (e.g., [60]) due to the rich information they can offer while having a relatively low cost, although they are time-consuming for processing [97]. “Smart collars” were ranked second, which accounted for 12.3% of the digital tools used in the selected research articles. This indicated a focus on individual animal tracking and behaviour monitoring (e.g., [56,76,98–102]). “Thermal cameras”, “weather stations”, “RFID/eid”, and “temperature

Fig. 6. Percentage of relevant articles per sensor type.

sensors” exhibited limited use, with each constituting to 5.5% of the selected research articles. Accordingly, “flow meters”, “force plates”, “moocal devices”, “multispectral cameras”, “hyperspectral cameras”, “GNSS”, “milk sensors”, and “smart feeders”, were employed less frequently (<5% of the selected research articles). This can be justified by the fact that these sensors cannot provide rich information (“RFID/eid”, “temperature sensors”, “flow meters”, “force plates”, “moocal devices”, “GNSS”, “milk sensors”, and “smart feeders”) or require high investment costs (“multispectral cameras”, “multispectral cameras”, and “hyperspectral cameras”) [103]. It is worth noticing that in many studies there was use of more than one digital tool (e.g., [58,69,80,102,104]). As many researchers have indicated, the use of multiple data sources can resolve ambiguities caused by the lack of information resulting from the use of a single data source [105,106].

Regarding the platform type used for the sensors in the various livestock settings (Fig. 7), “stationary systems” ranked first, constituting the overwhelming majority at 61.6% of all studies. This indicates that fixed-location sensors (e.g., [59,107]) and cameras (e.g., [108,109]) are the most common methods for data collection. As stated by other researchers, this platform type can provide continuous measurements and is best suited to environments with continuous power supply, such as those that mainly exist in indoor livestock farming [110–112]. Accordingly, “wearable technologies” were the second most prevalent category at 23.3%, highlighting the significance of on-animal sensors for monitoring individual health and behaviour [113,114]. “Mobile Ground platforms” were used in 13.7% of cases, while autonomous robotic platforms such as “UAVs” and “UGVs” were the least common, representing 6.8% and 4.1% of deployments, respectively, suggesting they are not yet mainstream tools in this area. This can be justified by their high investment and deployment costs [115], and the risk of causing stress to animals [116].

Fig. 7. Percentage of relevant articles per platform type.

3.3. Digital tools and contribution to transition to agroecology

As shown in Fig. 8 for the contribution to the transition to agroecology, the majority of articles (58.9%) focused on "Tier one: reduce inputs". "Tier three: redesign agricultural systems to incorporate biodiversity" ranked second and was accounted for 20.5% of the articles. "Tier five: create a just and equitable global food system" covered 17.8% of the articles, while "Tier two: substitute with sustainable inputs" was represented by 15.1%. Only a small percentage of articles (1.4%) delved into "Tier four: reconnect producers and consumers" which consequently ranked fifth. These results indicate that current research and tool development efforts remain concentrated on input reduction (Tier 1), with less attention to systemic changes and consumer-producer connections associated with higher tiers of agroecology [117,118]. This can be explained by the fact that efficiency and productivity take precedence over relational or systemic transformation [119], while there is a need for social mobilisation, governance reform, regulatory alignment and market access, which are still evolving [120,121].

3.4. Impact assessment of digital tools for livestock farming

Fig. 9 presents the perceived impacts of digital tools for livestock across social, environmental, and economic dimensions. In terms of social impact, the contribution of digital tools to "Human exposure to chemicals" is seen with "No effect" by a significant portion, though some digital tools can contribute to a "Large Decrease". Impact of digital tools on "Number and/or severity of accidents resulting in spills, property" and "Number and/or severity of personal injury accidents" exhibited varied responses, with a notable portion assigned to the "Large Decrease" category. On the other hand, digital tools in relation to "Amount of heavy physical labour", "Stress for farmer", and "Labour time" can contribute to "Large Decrease" or "Some Decrease". These results can be justified by the automation and consequently less frequent human presence that digital tools offer in various operations like milking [83], feeding [68] and monitoring [122].

From an environmental perspective, the use of digital tools can present "No effect" or a "Large Decrease" regarding "GHG emissions", while for "Biodiversity protection", "Water protection", "Soil protection", and "Air protection" are generally contributing to a "Large Increase" or "Some Increase". As it is stated by many researchers and concluded in the previous section, digital tools mainly contribute to reduced use of inputs while maintaining or increasing animal productivity [117,118]. Depending on the digital tool, this may lead to a lower use of natural resources and consequently to diminished GHG emissions and enhanced biodiversity protection [123–125].

Economically, regarding "Product wastage" digital tools were mainly assessed to contribute to "Large Decrease of product waste", while for "Product Quality" and "Shelf life of product", here digital tools, (depending on the type) are expected to contribute to a "Large Increase" or "Some Increase" of these characteristics. When focusing on digital tools contribution to "Input costs", results exhibited a mixed assessment, with mostly "No effect" or a "Large Decrease". Finally, for "Revenue, profit, farm income" and "Productivity", digital tools are expected to contribute to a "Large Increase" for all of them. This is in accordance with

Fig. 8. Percentage of relevant articles per tier of agroecology.

other researchers who also found enhanced profitability as a result of adoption of digital tools in livestock production [126–128]. It can be concluded from the above that digital tools in livestock production are largely perceived to have positive impacts, particularly as far as productivity and income, product quality, and labour requirements and environmental risks are concerned [129].

Similarly, the distribution of "All Impacts" assessment of the digital tools is relatively even, with "Low Impact" at 37%, "Medium Impact" at 31.5%, and "High Impact" also at 31.5% (Fig. 10). When focusing on "Economic and Environmental Impacts", "High Impact" presented the highest frequency at 42.5%, followed by "Medium Impact" at 30.1% and "Low Impact" at 27.4%. This suggests that the combined economic and environmental effects of these tools are more frequently perceived as significant. For the "Social Impact" category, the majority (50.7%) of the assessment fell into the "Low Impact" category, while "High Impact" was 37% and "Medium Impact" was only 12.3%. This indicates that the social effects of digital tools for livestock are more often considered to be less substantial compared to other categories. "Environmental Impact" presented a similar trend to "All Impacts", with contribution to "High Impact" ranked first at 39.7%, followed by "Low Impact" at 37.0%, and "Medium Impact" at 23.3%. Finally, "Economic Impact" alone showed the highest contribution to be at "High Impact" (49.3%), with "Medium Impact" and "Low Impact" at 28.8% and 21.9%, respectively. This suggests that digital tools for livestock can be used as enablers of agroecology and contribute to sustainable production, although they are predominantly perceived to have a significant positive economic influence, with social and environmental impacts less frequently emphasized in current research [129,130].

4. Study limitations

While this literature review is comprehensive, several potential limitations that warrant consideration should be acknowledged. First, the choice of keywords used in the query may have inadvertently excluded relevant articles that use alternative terminology, potentially resulting in an incomplete representation of the existing body of literature. Additionally, reliance on a single database for the literature search may introduce bias, as different databases index distinct sets of journals and publications. This limitation could restrict the scope and diversity of the retrieved studies and may potentially skew the findings towards the thematic emphasis of the selected database [131]. Also, the assignment of impact scores was conducted based on literature interpretation which may be connected with subjectivity and lack of field validation [132]. These limitations can be addressed in future studies by utilising more databases (e.g., Scopus) as well as by using more objective methodologies for the assessment of digital tools (e.g., benchmark datasets) [133].

5. Conclusions

This study aimed to map digital tools used in the livestock sector and assess their economic, environmental and social impact to identify their potential as enablers of agroecology. The PRISMA methodology was followed to identify relevant studies on livestock production in which digital tools were used. The screening process identified 73 articles for in-depth analysis. According to the results, the most common applications were for the monitoring of ruminants. For this reason, the most used digital tool category was RGB/RGB-D sensors and the most used platform was stationary platforms (e.g., automated milking systems, fixed location cameras, automatic feeders). Many digital tools addressed the first tier of agroecology, which corresponds to input reduction. This indicates that the digital tools developed and tested in livestock do not take into consideration systemic approaches in the development and testing phase of the digital tools. Moreover, the impact assessment indicated that the digital tools contribute positively in relation to the social, environmental and economic perspectives and consequently can

Fig. 9. Distribution of perceived societal, environmental and economic impact levels of digital tools adoption in livestock farming.

Fig. 10. Distribution of perceived impact levels (low, medium, high) of digital tools in livestock farming across social, environmental, and economic dimensions.

be used as enablers of agroecology. However, studies mainly focused on the economic perspective, with fewer references to environmental and social impacts. Future research on the digitalization of livestock production should focus more on the social and environmental impacts of digital tools by integrating appropriate frameworks in the tool development, as well as on the use of ground and aerial robots in various livestock settings. Finally, the digital tools should be co-designed and developed with farmers to ensure social acceptability and contribute to higher tiers of agroecology.

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During the preparation of this work the author(s) used QuillBot in order to improve the readability and language of the manuscript. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Evangelos Anastasiou: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Aikaterini Kasi-mati:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Georgios Papadopoulos:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation, Data curation. **Anna Vatsanidou:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation. **Marilena Gemtou:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation. **Friederike Schwierz:** Project administration, Investigation, Data curation. **Andreas Meyer-Aurich:** Project administration, Investigation, Data curation. **Spyros Fountas:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

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Supplementary materials

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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